

DIELECTRIC CHARACTERIZATION OF SNOW AT 24 GHz: INSIGHTS FROM A LOW-COST RADAR IN SODANKYLA, FINLAND

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ABSTRACT

Monitoring the internal structure of the snowpack is imperative for managing snow-related hazards like avalanches and snowmelt floods. The surge in availability of cost-effective, low-power, and low-profile 24 GHz frequency-modulated continuous-wave (FMCW) radars, originally designed for the automotive sector, has opened new possibilities. This paper illustrates the application of a compact and economical FMCW radar to enhance snowpack studies by swiftly providing the dielectric properties of snow and potentially assessing density and liquid water content (LWC). The radar functions as a snowpit instrument, creating expedited snow profiles of dielectric properties, aiming to overcome the drawbacks of slower, operator-dependent traditional density cutters. Initial results showcase the real part of the relative dielectric permittivity in actual snow conditions. Results are compared with manual measurements directly taken in the snowpit and with the bulk measurements taken with a well-established multi-band radar.

Index Terms— Snow, Snow Monitoring, Microwave Radar, Liquid Water Content, FMCW, Snow Density

1. INTRODUCTION

Analyzing the snowpack traditionally relies on human-operated manual techniques [1], where parameters like density and liquid water content (LWC) play a crucial role in gauging snowpack stability and forecasting ice melt during spring. This involves the use of well-known tools such as the density cutter and pocket scale, though their application introduces uncertainties. For instance, the measurement of snowpack density using cutters exhibits variations of up to 11% across different cutter types, not accounting for potential discrepancies in weighing devices [2]. Similarly, determining LWC commonly involves the gravimetric method, a procedure known for its complexity and time-intensive nature. In practice, operators often resort to visual inspection, leading to subjective results and increased uncertainties.

In addressing these challenges, various sophisticated instruments like the Snow Fork [4] and the Denoth probe [5]

have been proposed to refine in-situ snowpack analysis and enhance the coherence of density and LWC measurements. However, these instruments face drawbacks, including reliability issues, accuracy concerns [6], and high costs, rendering them less user-friendly. While frequency-modulated continuous-wave (FMCW) radars have gained prominence in remote sensing applications for snow measurements [7], their untapped potential as in-situ tools for studying snow properties warrants exploration. This paper introduces a novel approach, utilizing a commercially available next-generation FMCW radar operating at 24 GHz. Initially designed for collision avoidance and employed in previous snowpack thickness estimation [7], this radar is proposed for extracting snow density and LWC within the snowpack, presenting a promising solution as a regular profiling snow pit tool. Accompanied by a fixed metallic target (aluminum plate) positioned 30 cm from the antenna, the radar and metallic plate are inserted into the snowpack at varying heights to construct a comprehensive density and LWC profile. The radar is fully detailed in [10].

In this paper the first results for the real part of the relative dielectric permittivity of the snowpack are presented and compared with the outcomes of Snowave, a multi-band radar system able to deliver bulk measurements of the snowpack [11]-[13].

2. RADAR DESCRIPTION

For this work, the IMST's Sentire Radar Module operating at 24 GHz has been used. IMST's Sentire Radar Module stands out as an affordable, sleek, and exceptionally lightweight radar unit seamlessly integrated into a waterproof shelter. Operating in the K-band, it boasts a maximum bandwidth of 2.5 GHz. In the scope of this project, we utilized an integrated patch antenna, provided by IMST, featuring a single transmitter antenna and two receiver antennas. IMST offers proprietary commercial software for device testing, complemented by a comprehensive user interface for creating new software and expanding post-processing capabilities.

As a fixed target, a metallic plate has been attached to the radar placed at 30 cm from the antennas in order to delimitate the measurement area in the range direction. A picture of the

Fig. 1: IMST's Sentire Radar Module and reflector.

radar is shown in Fig. 1. Measurements in real snow are conducted by cutting two 'slots' in the snowpack for fitting the antennas and the reflector, this can be done easily with a snow saw. Subsequently, the antennas and the reflector are inserted into these two slots and the measure can be taken. Once the measurement is done, the system can easily slide down the snowpack. Fig. 2. shows a schema of the system.

3. EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGN

In April 2023, a 15-day campaign unfolded in the Arctic region, specifically at the Sodankylä-Tähtelä station in Finland (Fig. 3). Initially, the 70 cm snowpack exhibited a dry state with no apparent water content but had notably high density values. As temperatures rose in the subsequent days, humidity increased within the snowpack. By the campaign's conclusion, the snowpack had diminished by approximately 50% of its initial thickness. The initial liquid water content film at the surface transformed into vertical channels, permeating through the snowpack to the underlying soil, accumulating several centimeters of liquid water. After conducting a preliminary test to assess the measurement feasibility, snowpack observations were conducted once or twice daily for a fortnight. The results presented in this paper pertain specifically to the 18th of April 2023, and two subsequent days, situated in a bog site at approximately 67°22' N, 26°39' E. A picture of the bog site is shown in Fig. 3.

At the same time, multiple measurements using the Snowwave radar were conducted in L band (1-2 GHz) in a slightly varied position (within an area of approximately 1 m²), exploiting its non-destructive measurement capability. Thus, it is worth noting that the SNOWAVE radar is placed on the top of the snowpack, looking downward, with no need of snow pits, so retrieving information about the bulk, averaged, properties of the entire snowpack.

Fig. 2: Snowpit and a scheme on how the 24 GHz works.

Fig. 3: Bog site in Sodankylä-Tähtelä, Finnish Lapland.

As for the 24 GHz radar measurements, the snowpit underwent measurements at 5 cm intervals, starting from the top. Simultaneously, a traditional density cutter with a volume of 216 cm³ was employed to conduct measurements at the same 5 cm intervals. Dielectric values are inferred with these density measurements for comparison with the radar.

Temperature measurements were executed to ascertain the presence or absence of water, and the liquid water content (LWC) percentage was subsequently estimated using an SLF capacitive sensor.

4. RESULTS

As an example, results for the 18th, 19th and 20th of April for the real part of the relative dielectric permittivity (dielectric constant) are shown in Fig. 4. Results show the ability of the radar to produce snow profiles. Discrepancies with the ground truth are within expectations, and most notably the radar follows the trend of snowpack permittivity. Then, results for the bulk dielectric constant of the entire snowpack, derived averaging the values measured at 5 cm intervals, are shown in Table 1. Comparison with ground truth and with the L-band radar is also shown.

Fig. 4: Comparison between the dielectric constant measured by the 24 GHz radar (blue dots) and the dielectric constant retrieved by manual analysis (orange dashed line and orange dots), for different depths within the snowpack. Results for the 18th (top), 19th (middle) and 20th (bottom) of April 2024.

Tab. 1: comparison between 24 GHz radar, Snowwave and the manual analysis in terms of bulk dielectric constant of the entire snowpack. The value with the asterisk highlight a measure taken during a day where approx. 10 cm of water accumulated on the bottom of the snowpack.

	24 GHz RADAR	SNOWAVE (BULKY)	GROUND TRUTH
18/04/2023	1.78	1.90	1.54
19/04/2023	1.63	1.79	1.60
20/04/2023	2.00	2.62*	1.65

5. DISCUSSION

Results for the 24 GHz Sentire Radar are close with the ground truth measurements. However, some discrepancies are shown. The presence or moisture during all the measurements can have a strong impact on the accuracy of the measures, introducing losses in the system and making logistics more challenging. It is expected to achieve better accuracy working at lower temperatures with a dry snowpack.

With the radar it is also possible to estimate the imaginary part of the dielectric constant and hence, derive density and LWC, future developments of this work will go in the direction of achieving these metrics.

It is worth noting that working at this wavelength (~1.25 cm in the vacuum) implies getting closer to the size of snow crystals and hence, scattering effects can have their influence. However, the results presented in this work (based on the time-of-flight of the radar signal, and not on the power loss) seem not to be affected by them.

Snowwave, which can be operated at different bandwidth and for collecting the data presented in this paper was operate in the L band, returns dielectric constant values slightly greater than those obtained by the 24 GHz radar and by the manual analysis. This is because, its lower frequency and its ability to observe bulky features make it susceptible to the influence of the water film on the snowpack surface and the moisture at its base. This effect is magnified for the measurement taken on the 20th of April when, due to the high temperatures, the meltwater percolated into the snowpack, accumulating to approximately 10 cm at the bottom of the snowpack itself. This can be appreciated also observing that the bottom graph of Fig. 4, referred to the 20th of April, the manual analysis is missing for the first 10 cm of the snowpack, exactly for the reason that it was impossible to take, practically being a layer of water. However, using the Snowwave radar in L band, the signal was able to sense this bottom layer of water, and it is worth to note that even a few millimeters of propagation within this layer significantly elevate the volumetric dielectric constant, thus explaining the value reported in Table 1.

6. CONCLUSIONS

For the first time, results for characterizing real snow with a low-cost and portable 24 GHz radar have been presented in this paper. An FMCW 24 GHz was used for retrieving the dielectric parameters of the snow and an experimental campaign done in the Arctic during April 2023 was used to test the sensor. The first preliminary results of this campaign are shown here. Results are satisfactory and demonstrate that this sensor can be used to obtain measures of the real part of the relative dielectric permittivity of the in-situ snow. Further development will show the retrieval of the imaginary part of the permittivity, and an estimation of density and liquid water content.

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